

IR8, which has no gene for bacterial blight resistance, and IR1545, which has a recessive gene (*xa5*), were further evaluated for response to kresek infection at different ages. Plants were inoculated by dipping their roots in bacterial suspension for 5 minutes. All IR8 seedlings were infected at ages ranging from 9 to 32 days after seeding (DS). At 9 and 16 DS, IR1545 was as susceptible as IR8. But at 23 DS, 54% of the IR1545 plants were infected with kresek, and at 32 DS, 8% were infected. That indicates that kresek resistance is expressed not only between varieties but also within varieties at different ages.

When IR8, IR20, IR1545, and DV85, which differ in resistance to bacterial blight, were tested for kresek infection by the root-dipping method of inoculation with Pxo82, DV85 was infected less than the others. IR8, IR20, and IR1545 also differed in response to kresek at different inoculum concentrations.

Fourteen varieties were then evaluated in the greenhouse and in the field for kresek reaction against two isolates, Pxo61 and Pxo82. The varieties varied in reaction to the two isolates. In addition, the reactions of Ketan Lumba, Lakshini Lumba, IR8 (susceptible check),

and India Dular (resistant check) to the three Philippine pathotypes of *X. oryzae* for leaf blight indicated that their kresek reactions did not correlate with their leaf blight reactions.

On the basis of overall reaction to the two isolates in the greenhouse, India Dular was ranked as most resistant; the susceptible check IR8 ranked 13th of the 14 varieties. In the field test with the same inoculation method, India Dular was most resistant and IR8, most susceptible. Plants were scored at 21 days after inoculation in the greenhouse and at 6 weeks in the field.

Scoring for varietal resistance to kresek

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Because kresek is a systemic infection of bacterial blight, the scoring of infection at a certain time after inoculation should be standardized. In a preliminary greenhouse test, the percentage of kresek development was found to climax 3 to 4 weeks after inoculation by the root-dipping method. Experiments using IR8 were thus designed to determine the proper number of plants to serve as bases

for varietal testing and screening, and the optimal number of days after inoculation for scoring. Obviously, the higher the number of plants, the lower the coefficient of variation obtained on the basis of estimated standard error of the means. This holds true for the prolonged duration of infection after inoculation. For practical purposes, from 60 to 80 plants scored at any time from 21 to 24 days (C.V. = 13%) after inoculation seem adequate for greenhouse tests. In the field, a proper base is 100 hills/variety scored at the 5th week after artificial inoculation and transplanting.

rows in wooden boxes. A susceptible check, Taichung Native 1 (TN1), was planted as a border. At 1 week after sowing, the wooden boxes were transferred to a galvanized iron tray filled with water. Brown planthoppers that had been raised on TN1 were transferred to the seedlings. (The original source of the hoppers was a collection

Reaction of varieties to brown planthopper in the laboratory. Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India.

Designation	Origin	Damage rating ^a
Nira	USA	0
Aruvatham chormali	Malabar	1
Thone-lone-lon B.20	Burma	1
Morada	South Canara	1
Co 10	Tamil Nadu	1
ASD 11	Tamil Nadu	1
Arupatham Kuruvai	Coimbatore	3
Kuruvai kalyan	Tirunelveli	3
Moshanam	Chinglepet	3
Mutha samba	South Arcot	3
Velan samba	South Arcot	3
Ptb 15	Kerala	3
Ratna chooda	Ganjam	3
Gurida Akkalu	Ganjam	3
Menthi Bayahenda	Ganjam	3
Chennagi	Bellary	3
Seera Samba		
wild paddy	Sri Lanka	3
Bing Yang Chao	China	3
Changalisein	China	3
Itach-huning	China	3
Talichao	China	3
Glutinous variety	Burma	3

^aOn a scale of 1 to 9: 0 = immune; 9 = very susceptible.

Reaction of wild rice species to sheath blight

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Ten strains of wild species were raised in mud pots and inoculated with the sheath blight pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani* by the straw bit method. Their disease reactions were observed and recorded. *Oryza australiensis* and *O. nivara* were highly susceptible to the disease but *O. rufipogon* and *O. barthii* were resistant. The other wild rices were susceptible.

Nira, a brown planthopper-resistant variety

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During 1976 kharif and rabi, and 1977 kharif, the resistance to brown planthopper and stem borer of 844 bulk progenies, 804 single-plant selections, 988 germplasm entries, and 62 varieties were evaluated in the laboratory and in the field.

From 30 to 40 seeds of each rice strain screened were sown in 20-cm-long